

Kinetics and Structural Interpretation of Competitive Ligand Binding for NO Dioxygenation in Truncated Hemoglobin N

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Abstract

Conversion of nitric oxide (NO) to nitrate (NO_3^-) by dioxygenation (NOD) protects cells from lethal NO. Starting from NO-bound heme, the first step in converting NO to benign NO_3^- is the ligand exchange reaction $\text{FeNO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{FeO}_2 + \text{NO}$ which is still poorly understood at a molecular level. For WT truncated Hemoglobin N (trHbN) and its Y33A mutant the barrier for the exchange reaction differs by 1.5 kcal/mol compared with 1.7 kcal/mol from experiment. It is directly confirmed that the ligand exchange reaction is rate limiting in trHbN and that entropic contributions account for 75 % of the difference between WT and the mutant. Residues Tyr33, Phe46, Val80, His81 and Gln82 surrounding the active site sample different ensembles in the ligand-bound and transition state (TS), respectively, and are expected to control the reaction path. Through comparison with electronic structure calculations the TS separating the two ligand-bound states is assigned to a 2A state.

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Competitive ligand binding is ubiquitous in biological systems.¹ For inner-shell binding of O_2^- in Cu-Zn superoxide dismutase other ligands including N_3^- , OH^- or F^- have been identified as competitive inhibitors and a typical process is the displacement of water by the substrate.²⁻⁴ Other such ligand exchange reactions have been observed for antitimetastatic Ru(III) complex imidazolium [*trans*- $RuCl_4(1H-imidazole)(DMSO-S)$] (NAMI-A), where the DMSO ligand is replaced by water through the interaction of the complex with human serum albumin,⁵ or for (NO, H_2O) exchange in the heme-based sensor YddV.⁶ Typically, competitive reactions are operative under conditions where ligand 1 (L1) has a weaker affinity towards the protein than ligand 2 (L2) but is available in excess ($c[L1] \gg c[L2]$). This provides an organism with additional control in regulation.

A biologically relevant competitive process is the conversion of molecular oxygen (O_2) and nitric oxide (NO) to nitrate. Interaction of NO and molecular O_2 is ubiquitous in globins. Both ligands fulfill essential physiological functions: O_2 is responsible for respiration, involved in enzymatic oxidation reaction, and essential for maintaining concentration and strong memory⁷ whereas NO regulates smooth muscle relaxation⁸ and platelet aggregation in vascular tissues⁸⁻¹¹ and plays important roles in neurotransmission^{8,10,12} and influences mitochondrial respiration.^{13,14}

However, the two ligands also work in concert, specifically in the NO dioxygenation reaction where harmful nitric oxide is converted to benign nitrate to relieve nitrosative stress in bacteria¹⁵ and is relevant for NO-detoxification in blood.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ NO dioxygenation is essential for flavohemoglobins and truncated hemoglobins in bacteria as well as myoglobin and hemoglobin in mammals.²⁰ The reaction was first studied for Myoglobin (Mb)²¹ followed by studies focusing on nitrate formation in other globins using experimental and computational approaches.²²⁻²⁵ The reported *in vivo* concentrations of HbNO in blood^{26,27} ($\approx 5 \mu M$)^{28,29} are consistent with the finding that NO preferentially binds to the minor population of the va-

cant hemes in Hb under physiological conditions^{30,31} although direct (*in situ*) measurement of HbNO concentrations, e.g. using EPR spectroscopy, can be difficult.^{26,32} In addition, HbNO can form from the S-nitroso adduct Cys β 93 (Hb-SNO).^{30,31} ¹H NMR experiments provide evidence for the conversion of oxygenated Mb (oxyMb) to metmyoglobin (metMb) by reacting with NO.³³ From stopped flow experiments, the second order rate constants for the reaction of NO with oxyHb and oxyMb (process III, see equation 1) are 4.36×10^7 and $8.9 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively.²²⁻²⁴

Because two ligands are involved in competitive ligand binding, the dynamics around the active site involves collisions between and crowding of the ligands. Therefore, both, entropic and enthalpic effects are expected to contribute to the functionally relevant dynamics and the transition state is topologically challenging. If structural information about the TS would be available, the reaction pathway could be manipulated with much more confidence and propensities for different outcomes of the reaction could be rationalized in a considerably more informed fashion. This is of particular importance in enzyme design. However, usually little is known about the transition state which separates the two end points because it is short lived and hence difficult to directly characterize by experiment.

Here we demonstrate that the conformational ensemble and electronic properties of the transition state between NO and O₂-bound truncated Hemoglobin can be characterized using atomistic simulations. Despite various previous kinetic studies^{21,23,24,33,34} the mechanistic aspects of NO/O₂ competition in globins at a molecular level are poorly understood. The

very first step for dioxygenation is the ligand exchange reaction in which NO is displaced by O₂ (process II, see equation 1). The experimental first order rate found for the overall reaction (process I, see equation 1) is 1.0×10^{-4} to $4.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ depending on the protein.³⁵⁻³⁷ In all these cases the first step - replacement of NO by O₂ - is assumed to be rate limiting. However, such rates are often measured in a rather indirect way. For example, for the Fe^{II}-NO + O₂ reaction the NO-dissociation reaction in trHb(II)-NO + CO was considered.^{35,36} From this reaction the dissociation rate ($1.3 \pm 0.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) was measured. Next, the rate for NO₃⁻ formation (process I see equation 1, $1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) was obtained from optical measurements on the trHb(II)-NO + O₂ reaction and fitting to a single exponential decay. Such an approach is, however, not sensitive to potentially relevant intermediates and only reports on the overall reaction. To better understand competitive ligand dynamics and reactivity around the heme-iron computational methods are potentially useful provided that they are of sufficiently high quality.

Multi-state adiabatic reactive molecular dynamics (MS-ARMD) are a powerful means to follow ligand-binding and unbinding processes in condensed phase systems.^{38,39} This approach combines empirical energy functions to allow bond breaking and bond formation to take place with the sampling efficiency of conventional MD simulations to provide a quantitative understanding of whether and how temporal and structural changes are related.

Figure 1: The active site of truncated hemoglobin (ribbon representation) solvated in water. The side chains involved in the ligand exchange reaction are shown in licorice and line representations for bound Fe-NO and the transition state, respectively. The diatomic ligands are not shown. The color code for individual atoms: Fe (green), C (cyan), N (blue), O (red) and H (white).

Because electronic structure calculations for Fe-O₂ complexes are notoriously difficult (see SI) it was decided to base the parametrization of the Fe-NO and Fe-O₂ interactions solely on

experimental data. The experimentally determined dissociation energy of NO towards protonated iron tetrapyridylporphyrin is 24.0 ± 0.7 kcal/mol⁴⁰ whereas the dissociation energy of O₂ in myoglobin is 14.6 kcal/mol.⁴⁰ A similar dissociation energy (24.8 ± 0.7 kcal/mol) for Fe-NO was found for the doubly protonated iron tetrapyridylporphyrin which is an analog of the heme subunit.⁴¹ Hence, $D_e(\text{O}_2) = 14.6$ kcal/mol and $D_e(\text{NO}) = 24.0$ kcal/mol were used to describe the Morse potentials for Fe-O₂ and Fe-NO, respectively, and the remaining parameters β and r_e for both bonds were those from the literature.⁴²

Based on this parametrization the system (see Figure 1) was set up for MS-ARMD³⁸ (see SI) and umbrella sampling⁴³ (US) simulations for determining the free energy for ligand exchange using the progression coordinate $\rho = \frac{d_{\text{Fe-O}_2}}{d_{\text{Fe-NO}}}$ (for the free energy profile from US depending on the difference coordinate, see Figure S6). The free energy barrier associated with the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} - \text{NO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} - \text{O}_2 + \text{NO}$ reaction is 19.7 kcal/mol, see Figure 2. Using transition state theory, such a barrier corresponds to a rate of $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ which agrees well with rates from experiments (Process I, see equation 1) ranging from 1.0×10^{-4} to $4.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ depending on the protein considered and confirms that the ligand exchange reaction (process II, see equation 1) is the rate limiting step.^{35,36} This is also consistent with the fact that process III ($\text{Fe-O}_2 + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{Fe(III)} + \text{NO}_3^-$) is fast as it occurs on the 10 to 100 ps time scale.²⁵

Figure 2: Free energy profile including error bars for the ligand exchange reaction in WT trHbN from umbrella sampling (black trace). The structures of O₂-bound ($\rho = 0.25$), NO-bound ($\rho = 2.5$) and the transition state ($\rho \sim 1.0$) are also shown. The TS region is broad and involves a distributed structural ensemble. The red dashed line shows the free energy profile for the ligand exchange reaction for the Y33A mutant.

For a more complete characterization of the transition state, an additional 1 ns umbrella sampling simulation around the TS was carried out. The transition state ensemble sampled is broad, see Figure 2. From these simulations, 100 coordinates and velocities were collected, each separated by 10 ps. Using these initial coordinates and velocities, ligand rebinding simulations were performed for 100 ps, which occurs 86 out of the 100 simulations. 45 trajectories finish in an Fe-NO bound state, whereas 41 trajectories end up with Fe-O₂ and in 14 cases both ligands remain unbound. The rebinding fraction for the NO ligand is 52.3 % compared to 47.7 % for O₂. Hence, the transition state ensemble is representative of a true TS which is characterized by an equal probability for the two processes.⁴⁴

The electronic properties of the TS can be further characterized from DFT calculations. For

an ensemble of 50 structures energies of the (His-heme + O₂ + NO) system were determined in their ²A, ⁴A and ⁶A states. The correlation between the ²A and the MS-ARMD energies is $R^2 = 0.98$, whereas the ⁴A and ⁶A do not correlate at all (see Figure S1). Furthermore, it is found from additional DFT calculations that at infinite separation the ²A state correlates with either a ¹heme + ²(O₂ + NO) or a ³heme + ²(O₂ + NO) whereas other asymptotic states can be excluded (see Figure S2).

Experimentally, it is found that the NO dioxygenation rate depends on the particular type of globin, i.e. Ngb,^{35,45} Hb,^{35,36,46,47} or Mb.³⁶ For example, mutation of the Phe62 gate residue (controls the diffusion of ligands to the active site cavity through channel I) in trHbN to Trp, Tyr, Ala and Ile, decreases the overall rate for NO dioxygenation by a factor of two to three.⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ It has also been observed that the Y33A mutation leads to doubling the rate compared to the WT protein.^{46,51} This illustrates the importance of the environment which constitutes the active site for the NO dioxygenation reaction. To quantify the role of the active site residues in the ligand exchange reaction, separate 1 ns equilibrium MD simulations for the reactant and product states were carried out. The average protein structures from the simulations and the umbrella sampling at the TS ($\rho = 1.01$) were computed and compared. The most prominent differences for the WT are found in regions where His81 binds to the heme and in the active site (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Average protein structure of the three states: Fe-NO (yellow), Fe-O₂ (red) and the transition state (Fe + NO + O₂) (blue) (left panel). The most important differences between the three structures are encircled and labeled by A, B and C (active site and proximal site). Pockets in the reactant (upper right), product (right middle) and transition state (bottom right) are shown in yellow, red and blue spheres respectively. The extra pocket in the proximal side and the expanded pocket in the active site for transition state are shown in dotted ocher spheres (right bottom). The cavity/pocket volumes were computed using the GHECOM program.⁵²

The interplay between side chain orientation and ligand exchange was further characterized by comparing Ramachandran (Φ, Ψ) maps for the Fe-NO bound and transition state structures. The average Φ and Ψ values from the simulations for the Fe-NO + O₂ state are in accord with the X-ray structure of trHbN (see Figures 4 and S3).⁵³ Both Φ and Ψ angle distributions were computed for three active site residues: Tyr33, Phe46, Gln58. For Tyr33, $P(\Phi)$ in the reactant and TS state are very similar (see Figures 4 and 5) whereas the peak position and distribution for $P(\Psi)$ differ. Similar observations were made for Phe46 (see Figure S3 and S4). However, for Gln58, both distributions, $P(\Phi)$ and $P(\Psi)$ are very similar

in the two states (see Figures S3 and S4). Differences in $P(\Phi)$ and $P(\Psi)$ are also found for Val80, His81 and Gln82 (see Figures 4, 5 and S3) which are at the proximal site of the heme (see Figure 1). Most prominently, the Ψ -orientation of His81 between the reactant and the transition states changes by -70° . This is a consequence of the out-of-plane motion of the iron atom in the transition state compared to the bound state (see Figure 5). This rotation and the motion of the Fe-atom toward the proximal site lead to an increased size of the active site in the TS.

Figure 4: Distribution of Φ and Ψ angles of the side chains in bound Fe-NO and transition state for the wild type (WT) protein (left panel) and for the Y33A mutant (right panel). The black squares in WT indicate results from the X-ray structure.⁵³ The deviation for Q82 may be due to its solvent exposure, see Figure 1. The $(\phi_{\max}, \psi_{\max})$ values of Tyr33 in the Fe-NO and the TS for the WT are $(-70.0^\circ, -15.0^\circ)$ and $(-67.0^\circ, -7.0^\circ)$ respectively. On the other hand, for the Y33A mutant the values for Ala33 are $(-65.3^\circ, -26.6^\circ)$ and $(-63.5^\circ, -23.9^\circ)$ in the Fe-NO and TS respectively.

The insignificant changes in the probability distributions for Gln58 between the reactant and the TS (see Figure S4) indicate that this residue does not participate appreciably in the reaction and hence the overall rate should depend little on mutating this residue. This

is indeed found in experiments for which a minor increase from $(2.2 \pm 0.3) \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (WT) to $(2.6 \pm 0.4) \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Q58A) is found for nitrate formation.⁴⁶ Conversely, the width and position of the maximum of $P(\Psi)$ for Tyr33 differs appreciably between reactant and TS and for Val80 both, $P(\Phi)$ and $P(\Psi)$, change. Concomitantly, the rate coefficients increase by more than a factor of two (and hence the free energy barrier decreases by ≈ 1.7 kcal/mol based on transition state theory) upon Alanine mutation of these two residues, to $(4.6 \pm 0.9) \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $(4.7 \pm 0.6) \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, for the Y33A and V80A mutants, respectively.⁴⁶

To support these hypotheses, the free energy surface and reaction barrier height for ligand exchange was explicitly determined from umbrella sampling simulations for the Y33A mutant. In agreement with the above argument, the barrier height for the $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} - \text{NO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} - \text{O}_2 + \text{NO}$ reaction is lowered by $\Delta\Delta G = 1.5$ kcal/mol compared to WT, see Figure 2 which is close to the value determined from experiment (~ 1.7 kcal/mol) . The difference between WT and the Y33A mutant can be traced back to the stabilizing interaction between the ligands and the -OH group of the Tyrosine at position 33 in the WT protein which is absent in the Alanine-mutant.

The distributions $P(\Phi, \Psi)$ were also determined for Ala33 in the Y33A mutant, see Figure 4 and were found to be almost identical in the reactant and at the TS (see Figure S5). Hence, Ala33 participates little in the reaction. This is different from the situation in the WT where $P(\Phi, \Psi)$ for Tyr33 in the reactant and at the TS state differs.

Upon ligand dissociation (NO or O₂) from the heme the Fe atom moves below the porphyrin plane towards His81 which leads to further displacements of residues Val80, Gln82 and Gly83. This generates a new pocket on the proximal side in the TS with a volume of $\sim 30 \text{ \AA}^3$ which corresponds to the volume of one water molecule (see Figure 3). Also, the

size of the active site (distal site) pocket in the TS (197 \AA^3) expands by $\sim 40 \text{ \AA}^3$ compared to the Fe-NO bound state (157 \AA^3) due to the iron atom moving below the heme-plane and the movement of the Phe46 ring (Figure S4).

Comparison of the volume of the active site in the TS indicates an increase by more than 10% in pocket volume between the WT (197 \AA^3) and Y33A mutant (234 \AA^3). This increase in pocket volume increases entropy and hence decreases the free energy and the barrier for rebinding. This agrees with a decrease in the $\text{FeNO} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{FeO}_2 + \text{NO}$ barrier height for the Y33A mutant (red curve in Figure 2) compared to WT (black trace in Figure 2) by 1.5 kcal/mol. The decreased barrier for Y33A may be due to favorable entropic contributions. An enthalpic origin of that magnitude is unlikely due to the small dipole moments of both ligands. This was explicitly verified by computing average interaction energies (over 500 structures from 1 ns simulation in the TS) between the ligand and the surrounding protein which are -3.83 kcal/mol for the WT compared with -3.40 kcal/mol for the Y33A mutant i.e only a difference of $\Delta H = 0.4$ kcal/mol compared to $\Delta G = 1.5$ kcal/mol, leaving $-T\Delta S = 1.1$ kcal/mol for the entropic contribution of the overall process. It is also of interest to note that the interaction energies of the free ligands in the WT reactant (Fe-NO) and product (Fe-O₂) states are -2.7 and -2.8 kcal/mol, respectively, which suggests that in moving to the transition state a certain amount of entropic penalty is to be paid due to spatial constraints.

Figure 5: Distributions $P(\Phi)$ (black) and $P(\Psi)$ (red) of the Ramachandran angles for Fe-NO bound (solid line) and the transition state (dashed line) for WT protein. The distributions for the Fe-NO bound state (solid line) and TS state (dashed line) were built from 1 ns equilibrium and umbrella simulations $\rho = 1.01$ respectively.

Overall, the computed rate for the ligand exchange reaction (process II) of $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ compares well with experiments (process I) that range from 1.0×10^{-4} to $4.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ depending on the protein considered^{35,36} and is consistent with a 10 to 100 ps time scale ($k \sim 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$) for process III (NO_3^- formation).²⁵ Analysis of the conformational dynamics in the reactant and transition state suggests that Tyr33 and Val80 directly affect the rate of process II whereas Gln58 does not. This also agrees with experiments which find rate enhancements by more than a factor of two for the Y33A and V80A mutants but insignificant changes for the Q58A variant. Ramachandran maps for the reactant and TS structures suggest that the transition state in the WT is loose (more flexible) which is also found from analysis of the conformational ensemble, see Figure 4 and 5. On the other hand, the dissociating ligands never leave the active site. Hence, the present simulations provide a quantitative assessment of the ligand exchange reaction (process II) for both the WT and Y33A mutant of trHbN.

Unraveling the molecular mechanisms of ligand exchange reactions in general and for the present case in particular paves the way to address design questions related to controlling ligand motion and localization in the reactant, product and transition states. For the title

reaction the work clarifies that reduction of the barrier height for particular mutants (Tyr33) is due to both, enthalpic and entropic effects. While optimizing intermolecular interactions has been a general guiding principle in ligand design and optimization, controlling entropic contributions in design problems has proven to be considerably more difficult. Including these considerations is paramount for exploring the molecular basis of reaction mechanisms in enzyme catalysis.

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